

17-Tungstophosphodiarsenate(v) : Synthesis and Characterisation of Sodium, Guanidinium and Tetramethyl Ammonium Salts

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SODIUM, guanidinium and tetramethylammonium salts of mixed heteropoly oxoanion $[\text{As}_2\text{PW}_{17}\text{O}_{62}]^{-7}$ have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analyses, infrared spectroscopy and thermal analysis. The X-ray crystal structure of heteropoly tungstoarsenate or tungstophosphate anion of the type $[\text{X}_2^{\text{n}+}\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{62}]^{-(16-2\text{n})}$ where X=As or P is well-established^{1,2}. Weakley³ prepared a number of triheteropoly salts of the type $\text{M}_x[\text{X}_2\text{ZW}_{17}\text{O}_{62}\text{H}_2] \cdot \text{nH}_2\text{O}$, where M=K, $\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NH}_2$, X=As; Z= Mn^{2+} , Mn^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Co^{3+} , Ni^{2+} . The present work deals with the preparation and characterisation of some inorganic and organic salts of triheteropoly 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate where the ratio of W : P : As was found to be 17 : 1 : 2.

Sodium 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate(v) : Freshly prepared⁴ and analysed arsenic acid (1 g) dissolved in water (25 ml) was gradually added to an aqueous solution (150 ml) of sodium tungstate (17.85 g) with constant stirring for 0.5 h and the mixture was warmed for 1 h on a water-bath. To the above hot mixture aqueous solution (15 ml) of disodium hydrogen phosphate (1.15 g) was added with stirring maintaining pH of the solution at 2.5 using acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer. The mixture was then refluxed for 3 h, concentrated and left for crystallisation at 5°. The resulting pale yellow small needle-like crystals were washed with alcohol and analysed (Found : W, 62.15 ; P, 0.051 ; As, 3.40 ; Na, 3.12 ; O, 31.28. $\text{Na}_7[\text{As}_2\text{PW}_{17}\text{O}_{62}] \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : W, 65.85 ; P, 0.044 ; As, 3.15 ; Na, 3.38 ; O, 27.58%) ; molecular formula was assigned

TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF THE HETEROPOLY COMPOUNDS

[As ₂ PW ₁₇ O ₆₂] _x ·H ₂ O X=	ν _{H₂O}	δ _{H₂O}	ν _{W-O}	ν _{W-O-W}	ν _{P-O}	ν _{As-O}
Na	3 460s, b	1 625m, b	905s 860s 745m, b	785m, b 820s	1 065m 1 072s	455s 460
C(NH ₂) ₃	3 440s, b	1 620m, b	900s 880m, b 760s	800m 810s	1 075m 1 080s	440s 450
N(CH ₃) ₄	3 920s, b	1 615m, b	890m, b 860m 765m	810s 785m	1 070 1 080s	455 445s

on the basis of the parent heteropoly anion [X₂⁺W₁₈O₆₂]⁻⁽¹⁶⁻²ⁿ⁾ as confirmed by Dawson¹.

Guanidinium 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate(v): The guanidinium salt of the heteropoly anion [As₂PW₁₇O₆₂]⁻⁷ was prepared by metathesis of the sodium salt. A solution of sodium 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate(v) (7.03 g) in hot water (75 ml) was treated with a 10% (w/v) aqueous solution of guanidinium chloride. The mixture was digested on a water-bath for 0.5 h, then ice-cooled and the resulting yellowish solid was air-dried (Found: C, 1.69; H, 1.37; N, 2.12. [C(NH₂)₃]₇[As₂PW₁₇O₆₂].10H₂O calcd. for C, 1.78; H, 1.31; N, 2.08%).

Tetramethyl ammonium 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate(v): It was prepared by reacting a solution of sodium 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate(v) (6.19 g) in water (100 ml) with a 10% (w/v) aqueous solution of tetramethyl ammonium chloride by the analogous method as described above. The resulting deep yellow solid was air-dried and stored over sodium sulphate decahydrate as the compound was very efflorescent (Found: C, 6.95; H, 2.12; N, 2.07. [N(CH₃)₄]₇[As₂PW₁₇O₆₂].8H₂O calcd. for: C, 6.77; H, 2.01; N, 1.97%).

The complete analysis of the compounds were done by chemical and instrumental methods using alkali degraded solution of the samples. Tungsten was estimated⁵ by precipitating it as tungstic acid with HCl and cinchonine hydrochloride and igniting it at 780°, followed by weighing as WO₃. Phosphorus was estimated gravimetrically as magnesium ammonium phosphate after a preliminary separation as ammonium phosphomolybdate⁶ and arsenic was estimated by precipitating it as ammonium uranyl arsenate and weighing as uranous uranate⁷. Sodium was estimated by flame photometry. The solution of sodium salt of [As₂PW₁₇O₆₂]⁻⁷ anion was examined spectrophotometrically in various buffer solutions. It appeared to be most stable at pH 2.8–3.5. The intense broad absorption band of the sodium salt at approximately 3.9 × 10⁻³ cm⁻¹ (ε 5.2 × 10⁴) in uv region is ascribed to charge transfer from oxygen to tungsten which is a characteristic of polytungstates⁸. Infrared spectra of guanidinium carbonate and tetramethyl ammonium chloride were recorded for comparison with ir spectra (KBr) of the heteropoly salts. The positions and assignments of the main bands are given in Table 1.

All the compounds revealed distinct bands at 740–980 cm⁻¹, characteristics of polytungstates³. The bands at 740–925 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the independent W–O stretching vibration and broad bands at 785–820 cm⁻¹ to the W–O–W bridge vibration^{9,10}. The medium and sharp bands at 1 065–1 080 cm⁻¹ may be due to P–O stretching¹¹ and those at 440–462 cm⁻¹ correspond to tetrahedral AsO₄ linkage^{11,12}.

The thermal analysis of the sodium 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate(v) has been done by DTA and TGA. The salt showed characteristic endothermic peak corresponding to dehydration. The first large endothermic peak was observed within 150° indicating the loss of water of crystallisation, confirmed by the corresponding loss of weight of the salt. On further rise of temperature upto 300°, two more endotherms were observed, which may be due to further loss of water molecules. When temperature was raised further, no peaks in the thermograms nor any loss in weight of the salt was observed upto 500°. At 550 ± 20°, a sharp exothermic peak was recorded followed by loss in weight and decomposition of the salt to the corresponding oxides, which was confirmed by elemental analyses. The exotherm at this high temperature indicated the total loss of water of constitution of the salt followed by decomposition of the heteropoly anionic cage which was confirmed by observing the physical change in colour of the salt and total insolubility of the residual products in water. The ir spectra of the ignited sample at this stage showed the absence of bands at 3 360–3 440, 1 620–1 660 and 590–640 cm⁻¹, which are characteristic bands for water of crystallisation (ν_s + ν_{as} OH of lattice water), bending mode of lattice water and vibrational mode of constitutional water respectively^{9,12}.

Guanidinium 17-tungstophosphodiarsenate underwent a weight loss of 3.82% on heating to 250° and decomposed (turned black) at 300°. The tetramethyl ammonium salt lost not more than 13.33% in weight on heating to 300° for 3 h with dark brown colour change giving rise to a sticky mass.

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